

ISLAM BANKS: FEATURES, PROBLEMS, DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Annotation. For half a century, Islamic banks have become known for not recognizing the charging of interest for transactions with money, which is categorically condemned in Islam as usury, and participate in the investment process as business partners, sharing all the risks for the funded project. Bank profits are generated from the income from the capital placed in such a project, which is forbidden to keep in the pot, which puts it entirely at the service of society, contributing to the idea of an even distribution of benefits and social justice.

Keywords: Islamic banking, Islamic financial industry, financial business, assets, microfinance.

Introduction. The market of Islamic financial services is developing rapidly: in the period from 2006 to 2011, the average annual growth of global Islamic financial assets was 18.82% [1]. The leading positions are occupied by Islamic banks, currently accumulating from 900 billion to 1 trillion dollars [2, p. 57], or more than 90% of Islamic financial assets [3, p. 2]. The global financial crisis has called into question the advantages of the Western financial system. However, traditional financial institutions and instruments still prevail. It is noteworthy that even in the financial markets of Muslim countries, the share of Islamic banks is relatively small on average (less than 20% of the banking assets of Muslim countries [4, p. 25] and about 1% of global banking assets [5, p. 78]). The importance of the market of Islamic financial services in general and Islamic banks in particular is assessed ambiguously. The importance of the market of Islamic financial services in general

and Islamic banks in particular is assessed ambiguously. Opponents of the Islamic financial system note not only its competitive disadvantages [6, p. 205], but also the possible social danger [7, p.298]. Apologists of Islamic financial principles, on the contrary, consider the institution of loan interest as a source of social injustice, concentration of capital, reduction of demand, and unbalanced economy [8]. As an alternative, the concept of profit and loss sharing (PLS) is proposed, which, in their opinion, creates conditions for a more even distribution of profits and thereby reduces income differentiation in society, promotes a more efficient allocation of resources, and assumes more complete control over the business by a financial intermediary. — an Islamic bank that assumes most of the financial, investment and business risks, which together reduces the risk of financial crises and creates the prerequisites for sustainable economic growth.

What are the possible prospects for the development of Islamic banks and what are the challenges facing the Islamic banking industry? This article is devoted to the study of these issues, taking into account the peculiarities of the functioning of Islamic financial institutions. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze the organizational, legal and financial foundations of the functioning of Islamic banks: the essence of Islamic financial principles, the structure and models of regulation of the Islamic banking system, the operations and features of Islamic banks as financial intermediaries, their competitive advantages and disadvantages.

Principles and organizational and legal bases for the functioning of Islamic banks An Islamic bank is a financial institution that accepts deposits and places borrowed funds in accordance with the principles that are expressed in the prohibitions of loan interest, speculation and such contractual conditions that cause uncertainty and (or) one party receives excessive amounts of property at the expense

of the other [9]. These principles correspond to the ideas of Musulman about a fair (non-exploitative) distribution of income in society: a person receiving income should take part in the labor process and (or) risk their property [10, p. 332], and earn money from money is not allowed.¹ From an organizational and legal point of view, the necessary conditions for the operation of Islamic banks are the following: the presence of a Sharia supervisory board, designed to ensure that all operations comply with the requirements of Sharia²; the ability to conduct banking operations on the basis of Islamic financial principles (including observing the prohibition of loan interest³); the absence of legal restrictions on the participation of banks in trading operations and on the distribution of profits (losses) with customers.

It is obvious that ensuring such conditions requires a special approach to the regulation of Islamic banks — in practice, three models are implemented in which: 1) banking legislation is built in accordance with the requirements of Sharia (Sudan and formally Iran and Pakistan); 2) the activities of traditional banks are regulated by general banking legislation, and Islamic banks are regulated by special laws (similar banking systems operate in Malaysia, Bahrain, Turkey, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, etc.); 3) the activities of Islamic banks are regulated within the framework of general banking legislation (this model is typical for most Western countries where Islamic banks are represented, such as the United Kingdom, Switzerland, and the United States) (for more information, see [13]).

¹ It should be noted that disputes about the social significance of loan interest have a very long history in Western civilization [10, p. 103-122]. According to medieval scholastics, it was considered an unforgivable sin when intermediaries profited by exploiting public needs. Subsequently, these ideas were developed in the labor theory of value.

² Sharia (Arabic. sharia, lit. - the proper way) — a set of Muslim legal and theological norms, proclaimed by Islam as the "eternal and unchangeable" fruit of divine institutions. Sharia is often called Muslim law [11, p. 1362].

In the structure of the Islamic banking system, there are two following levels::

1) international non-profit organizations that promote the development of Islamic banks (the key institution at this level is the Islamic Development Bank (IDB), which provides various support to Islamic financial institutions, including acting as a financial intermediary, accepting deposits and placing funds in accordance with the requirements of Sharia); 2) commercial organizations, which, in turn, is represented by: a) commercial Islamic banks with the main goal of making a profit by providing Sharia-compliant banking services; b) specialized Islamic banks created to solve specific tasks (agricultural, industrial banks, etc.); c) Islamic windows in traditional banks (an important condition for the work of such units is "self-sufficiency as an Islamic financial intermediary" [14]: managed funds are invested in Sharia-compliant assets) [15, p. 116].

Financial characteristics of Islamic banks Unlike traditional banks, the financial intermediation of Islamic banks is based on the share of profit (loss) from transactions with real assets. The Islamic Bank provides and raises funds on specific terms: interest rates on both loans and deposits are not allowed.

To the greatest extent, the concept of profit and loss participation corresponds to the instruments of equity project financing of mudarab and musharak, the urgent nature of which does not allow them to be classified as equity financial instruments in the strict sense of the word [16, p. 4]. Active operations of Islamic banks on debt-free financing are executed by such major financial instruments as murabaha, salam, istisna'. They are not directly related to the concept of profit and loss participation, but are based on transactions with real assets and, therefore, exclude the exchange of money for money.

We will describe the features of the main financial instruments used in the active operations of the Islamic bank in more detail.

Mudaraba: a trust financing agreement under which the Islamic bank: finances the investment project, but does not have the right to participate in the management of this project; receives the due share of the profit from the project, while the profit is divided in pre-determined proportions between it and the partner managing the funds raised; bears all risks associated with non-receipt of profit on the project.

Musharaka: a joint venture agreement, under the terms of which a joint company is created for the implementation of an investment project, and one of its partners is an Islamic bank. Unlike mudaraba, in this case, the bank has the right to participate in the project management along with another partner (s), which partially reduces its risks. The financial result (both profit and loss on the project) is distributed in accordance with the participation interest.

Murabaha: a commercial loan agreement under which an Islamic bank, acting as an intermediary, at its own expense, but on behalf of the client, purchases a certain asset (product) according to the description provided by the client in the application. The description describes the essential characteristics of the asset, its price, and its availability on the market. The contract comes into force after the goods become the property of the intermediary. Then the product is sold to the customer at a price that includes a margin, usually on a deferred or installment payment basis.

Salam: a commercial loan agreement that provides for the purchase and sale of an asset (product) on a prepayment basis. According to the contract, the Islamic bank provides the contractor with a certain amount equal to the cost of the goods, and the contractor undertakes to deliver the goods by the agreed deadline. Salam is concluded simultaneously with another pre-dialect. As a rule, this is a parallel salam,

according to which the Islamic bank, in turn, acts as a performer, making a profit due to the difference in prices at which it buys and sells goods.

Istisna': a contract for the performance of works on the terms of prepayment, under which the Islamic bank provides the contractor with a certain amount equal to the cost of the work on the production of goods, and the latter undertakes to perform the work by the specified deadline. It is concluded in combination with another contract under which the Islamic bank sells the goods to the customer. The profit of the bank acting as an intermediary between the manufacturer and the final buyer of the goods is formed due to a pre-established difference in the purchase and sale prices: the price at which it pays for the performance of work is obviously lower than the price at which it sells the received goods. Most often, istis na' is used to finance large projects, as well as for mortgage lending.

Passive operations of Islamic banks are mainly carried out on the basis of shared project financing agreements and interest — free loans; the most popular financial instruments are mudaraba, card hasan.

Mudaraba: a contract whereby the depositor's funds are transferred to the Islamic bank's investment account, which is used to finance the investment project (s). The investor's share in the project financing is significant (up to 90%) [15, p. 98], and its profit depends on the financial result of the project. Mudara ba can be limited (related to a specific project) and unlimited (the bank itself determines where to invest).

Card hasan³: an interest-free loan agreement, under which the Islamic bank raises funds free of charge, can use them at its discretion, but is obliged to return

³ The khasan card (good loan — translated from Arabic) is used by Islamic banks mainly for solving socially oriented tasks: it is widely used for the development of small businesses, as well as for supporting clients experiencing financial difficulties [17, p.133].

them on demand. The funds received in this way are transferred to savings accounts. At the same time, Islamic banks try to encourage customers, for example, by providing them with discounts on their services. Other savings account formation mechanisms include the following: a) the bank has the right to use the raised funds, guaranteeing their return within the prescribed period, but at its discretion may pay additional income to the depositor; b) the raised funds may be invested by the bank, and the received profit may be divided with the depositor in pre — determined proportions.

As follows from the above, the most fundamental differences in the activities of Islamic and traditional banks are related to the concept of risk management and methods of raising and placing funds (table).

The activities of Islamic banks are characterized, of course, by specific principles. Therefore, the results of empirical studies are quite intriguing, according to which the differences between Islamic and traditional banks are not as critical as is usually assumed.

So, T. Beck, A. Demirguchkunt and O. Merrosh, having analyzed the activities of 2,857 traditional and 99 Islamic banks from 141 countries of the world for the period 1995-2007, did not reveal any significant features of Islamic banks either in terms of business model, or in terms of efficiency, asset quality or the level of stability of the dialect. As a rule, this is a parallel salam, according to which the Islamic bank, in turn, acts as a performer, making a profit due to the difference in prices at which it buys and sells goods.

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The competitive disadvantages of Islamic banks are usually studied in the context of the peculiarities of the development of the market of Islamic financial services, as well as in comparison with traditional financial institutions. According to Y. M. Mirkin, "within the framework of Islamic finance (taking into account the hierarchy inherent in Islamic society), it is difficult to expect a mass retail investor in securities, taking high risks, focused on large-scale and liquid stock markets" [6, p.205]. As a result, the market structure becomes simplified, the share of banks is

excessive, and there is a predominance of large family investors in joint-stock capital. T. Kuran is even more categorical, arguing that at this stage of development — in conditions of weak organization and lack of appropriate skills — the Islamic banking model is basically unviable [21, p. 35].

To what extent does the criticism of Islamic banks correspond to the results of empirical research? An analysis of the competitiveness of Islamic banks conducted by Ernst & Young in 2012 led to conclusions about a relatively more significant decline in the profitability of their business against the background of global financial instability and an insufficient level of "risk appetite" compared to traditional banks. In addition, it is emphasized that the practice of risk management applied by Islamic banks requires serious improvement [22, p. 29, 61]. The first conclusion sounds quite unexpected: in the context of the global financial crisis, Islamic banks as a whole proved to be more stable than traditional ones, demonstrating both a higher growth in lending volumes and a more significant increase in assets.

In the period from 2007 to 2009, the average growth rate of assets of Islamic banks was more than twice as high as that of traditional banks [18, p. 46]. However, this situation is explained not only and not so much by the higher efficiency of the Islamic banks, but also by the lower level of integration into the global financial system, which obviously hinders their development. The share of Islamic banks in the global banking system is relatively small and unevenly distributed, which suggests regional business fragmentation.

An undeveloped market infrastructure hinders the effective management of the liquidity of Islamic banks. The level of their liquidity exceeds that of traditional banks by 40%, which is explained both by the insignificant depth of the money

market due to the small number of its participants, and by the insufficient number of instruments that could be used in the corresponding operations with the central bank [18, p. 47]. In order to solve this problem in 2010, The International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation (IILM) was established to issue highly liquid short-term financial instruments that meet the requirements of Sharia law. An important role in the development of the infrastructure of the Islamic financial market is played by the International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM), founded in 2001 and launched in 2002.

The imperfection of banking supervision and regulation is noted as one of the most serious challenges for the Islamic banking industry [23, p. 32]. The most significant work in this direction is carried out by the Islamic Financial Services Boards (IFSB), which develops general standards for the activities of Islamic financial institutions, and the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), which approves both specialized (accounting, auditing) and general standards for the activities of Islamic financial institutions. However, the introduction of international standards for the activities of Islamic financial institutions raises serious concerns among many experts, since the Islamic financial market in different countries is very unevenly developed [24, p. 2].

In general, despite the serious infrastructural and organizational challenges facing the Islamic banking industry, the prospects for its development are very positive. According to the most cautious forecasts published by Moody's Investor Service back in 2008, the global potential of the Islamic banking market was \$ 4 trillion [16, p. 1], which is several times higher than its current volume. In this regard, it is impossible to ignore the demographic factor: the number of the Muslim population on a global scale is increasing. By 2030 the proportion of Muslims will

exceed 25% of the world population [25] (in 1950, the corresponding figure did not exceed 13-14% [26]). The demographic factor is of great importance, since the peculiarity of Muslim civilization is its "close connection with religion, which is a way of life, a system of values, and socio-political and economic institutions" [27, p.129]. And, consequently, the Islamization of financial relations in the Muslim civilization becomes quite a natural phenomenon. Under these conditions, the volume of supply of Islamic financial services does not correspond to the growing demand: only 12% of Muslims use Islamic financial products [3, p. 2] and 14% use banking services in general, while in the United States and Great Britain, the same indicator is 92 and 95% for households, respectively [5, p. 73].

It is very significant that in recent years, a growing number of Western companies have turned to Islamic financial institutions and instruments not only to diversify their investments, but also to attract foreign investment, as well as in cooperation with partners from Muslim countries. As a result, not only Islamic financial institutions are rapidly developing, but also the "Islamic divisions" of traditional financial institutions that compete for domestic and foreign clients. It is believed that in the future, the main trends in the development of Islamic banks will be associated with the processes of simplification and standardization of the products offered, as well as with the consolidation of the industry [28; 2, p. 57].

Summing up the above, it should be noted the social role of Islamic banks involved in the financing of low-profit infrastructure projects that stimulate the development of small and medium-sized businesses, increasing the availability of financial resources, including for the poorest groups of the population, through special micro-credit programs [2, p. 62]. In the end, "it is impossible not to see" that

the Islamic banking model is initially based on and solves the problem of overcoming a number of social problems of society [20, p. 125].

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